

Somatic Genome Editing: Technical Challenges and Ethical Appraisal

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Abstract

The ability to modify the DNA sequences with molecular tools that employ nucleases has made it possible to edit genomes. Somatic genome editing is the procedure to alter the genome of somatic cells, making the changes introduced into the nucleotide sequence not inheritable. Powerful tools have been developed for therapeutic purposes to correct monogenic inherited disorders that often cause premature death and for which effective treatment options are not available. To ensure positive impact and minimise potential harms of these techniques, require to understand their limits in addition to apply values and principles that guide their use. This study reviews technical challenges of genome editing and appraises the Ethics of its application.

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Introduction

“The technology of human genome editing can be used to expand human knowledge, improve human health and contribute to both collective well-being and the common good. To maximize the positive impact and minimize the potential harms of this technology, procedural and substantive values and principles should guide policies and practices [1].”

Genome editing encompasses several techniques to modify DNA in the genome of cells in a living organism, thereby altering the information encoded at a target site [2]. Human genome therapy refers to changes made in the DNA sequence for the purpose of treating disorders of genetic origin. It has broader scope than gene therapy that alters coding regions of the genome, because genome therapy can alter also non-coding sequences in the genome.

Human genome editing techniques can be used on somatic cells (non-heritable), germline cells (not for reproduction) and germline cells (for reproduction) [2]. Generally, somatic genome editing (SGE) is considered

less ethically problematic than germline genome editing because its effects are not passed on to future generations. Genetic editing tools also can be used to enhance human traits, such as resistance, strength, or cognitive capacity. Such interventions can target somatic cells in adults or be employed in embryos during early development, such that introduced genomic alterations will affect the germline and propagate through future generations.

Somatic genome editing is well suited for therapeutic purposes of monogenic inherited disorders in which mutations in a single gene are the cause of diseases often causing premature death and for which effective treatment options are not available; for example, cystic fibrosis and severe combined immunodeficiency [3]. Therapeutic applications of SGE have had notable successes with T-cell therapies, which offer great promise in cancer treatment [4]; more recently, SGE has been used to cure patients suffering from a form of retinal blindness called Leber congenital amaurosis, and as treatment for the blood disorder haemophilia B

[5]. Genome editing systems also could facilitate the rapid screening of new drugs and promote the development of personalised medicine, connecting genomics, disease phenotypes and therapeutic goals [6].

This study assesses technical challenges present in the application of genetic editing methods and appraising the ethics of employing SGE for therapy or enhancement.

Technical Challenges

Editing the Genome

“The need to develop technology carefully, with robust testing and quality assurance measures in place to maximize benefit and minimize harm. The balance between benefit and harm, safety and speed, and innovation and access are relevant to all of human genome editing” [7].

The two broad approaches to these genome treatments are *ex vivo* and *in vivo* genome therapy. In *ex vivo* genome therapy, cells from a patient with a particular genetic condition are moved, edited in a laboratory to correct genetic defects in DNA or RNA sequences, and regrafted back into the person. This autologous procedure circumvents potential immune rejection of the genetically altered cells since the cells are derived from the patient to be treated. *In vivo* genome therapy introduces therapeutic DNA directly into affected cells of the patient. A major challenge of *in vivo* genome editing is to achieve specificity, namely, that the therapy only alters the intended tissues [8]. An example of *in vivo* somatic genome therapy is nasal spray containing functional cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulatory genes, developed for the purpose of treating congested lungs that result from cystic fibrosis [9].

Changes in the sequences of genomes have been induced by employing as genome-editing tools, nucleases programmed to target specific regions. The three main examples of enzymes that have been engineered for use in mammalian cells are (i) zinc-finger nucleases (ZFN) composed of two zinc-finger domains fused with a FokI endonuclease [10]; (ii) transcription activator-like proteins nucleases (TALEN) composed of repetitive amino acid sequences that act as transcription factors (TALE) fused with a FokI domain [11]; and (iii) the clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR) and CRISPR-associated nucleases (Cas) of bacterial and archaea defences, the CRISPR-Cas systems were adapted as gene editing tools by using a guide RNA for recognition of the target genomic sequence and the couple with high efficient Cas proteins [12]. The mechanism of action of these nucleases is to generate a double-strand break (DSB) at a specific locus, and to allow the endogenous double-strand repair machinery to insert a new sequence using a donor DNA template [13].

The current genome editing toolbox also includes methods that do not rely on endogenous repair mechanisms, such as prime editors and base editors, which can modify the host’s sequence without induction of DSB.

Base editors are enzymes composed of a fused single-stranded DNA deaminase and a catalytically impaired Cas9. They can introduce single-nucleotide variants in the genome of living cells with high precision and without generating DSB, events that pose risks of genotoxic events. They are effective at any stage of the cell cycle at variance with nucleases that rely on DSB repair and are more effective on dividing cells. A limitation of base-editing techniques is that they can only change a single nucleotide at a time [14].

CRISPR-Cas Nucleases

An important advance in genome editing techniques was the discovery, characterisation and development of the CRISPR-Cas system for editing the genome of eukaryote cells. It allowed for precise and controllable editing of specific cells, and opened a broad horizon of potential human clinical applications including correcting congenital monogenic disorders, targeting disease-causing molecular lesions, and altering multiple genetic loci at the same time [12]. The CRISPR-Cas9 system has been applied also to remove entire chromosomes in murine and human cell cultures suggesting a potential for the therapeutic treatment of human aneuploidy diseases resulting by supernumerary chromosomes [15].

The CRISPR-Cas technique is a simpler, more direct, and less expensive method for somatic genome editing than ZFN and TALEN. The efficiency of CRISPR-Cas depends substantially on the number of somatic cells that can be edited; nonetheless, its potential and ease of use suggest that human genome editing could become a way to treat some human genetic diseases at the individual level as a step towards the implementation of precision medicine [15], which is “An individualized approach to disease diagnosis and treatment, which uses various molecular profiles to select precise therapies and to develop new treatments [16].”

Challenges in the Application of the CRISPR-Cas9 Tool

Genome editing to modify a specific region in a large genome has the technical challenge to yield a predictable outcome without causing unintended secondary modifications and/or effects [12]. A goal of translational medicine is to develop somatic genome editing into an effective therapy [5]. However, specificity, effectiveness, and on- and off-target side effects are matters to be addressed to translate CRISPR-Cas to the clinical setting [6].

1. Safety and Effectiveness

Genome editing systems have been improved in the past 20 years, and adverse events are becoming rarer. Nevertheless, knowledge of technological risks is still

incomplete. In contrast, medical risks associated with other interventions such as organ transplantation and stem cell therapies have become more acceptable, likely because the risks involved in those procedures are better understood [3].

Editing *ex vivo* the genome of stem cells of a patient's affected tissue is an important therapeutic strategy in the treatment of genetic diseases. Nonetheless, the safety and effectiveness of the technique is limited because to recover, edit and regraft autologous stem cells from a patient is complex. Furthermore, another limitation is that stem cells perform homologous recombination inefficiently and tend to repair double-strand breaks by non-homologous end-joining which is an error-prone mechanism that often introduces deletions or insertions of nucleotides at the break site, and thus creates mutations [12].

2. On-Target Side Effects

Double-strand breaks (DSB) generated by CRISPR-Cas9 may also lead to on-target genome alterations. Besides the types of insertions, deletions, translocations, and rearrangements, on-target effects include large chromosome deletions, chromosome truncations, and homozygosis of the genome by inter-homology repair. Currently, no single method could detect all these types of off-target mutations, especially when they occur at a very low frequency [17].

More importantly, repair events or a genomic rearrangement of DSB is also a safety concern in CRISPR-Cas9-based therapeutic interventions. Although this technology can induce desired changes in the genomic sequences, the poorly understood and less controlled DNA repair mechanism is associated with the undesirable risk of biological dysfunctions. Deletion of a few kilobases in the neighbouring CRISPR-Cas9 nickase activity, unexpected insertion (incorrect or partial) of donor DNA sequence to the site of integration, and inversion are also unpredictable consequences of DNA repair mechanisms which must result in unexpected mutations [18].

3. Off-Target Side Effects

A major obstacle of this technology are off-target effects, that in some instances may be due to the genome having more than one perfect match for the guide RNA [19]. Responses to combat off-target effects include alteration of amino acids in Cas9 to improve its specificity and the design of new algorithms to refine the design of guide RNA [19]. In the future, researchers must improve genetic tools to eliminate off-target effects and to increase genome edition efficiency. Despite this problem, genome editing offers new opportunities for disease treatment, such as Acute Lymphoblastic Leukaemia, that have been beyond the reach of previous therapies [6].

Off-target effects are common in human cell cultures with persistent Cas9 expression and less common in *in*

vivo models. These effects in cell cultures may arise from various factors, including cell type, expression level, transfection method, cell culture maintenance, consecutive nuclease expression, guide sequence, and repair events [18].

The CRISPR-Cas9 system has been used to remove entire chromosomes from the genome, specifically the sex chromosomes from mouse cultured cells, embryos, and tissues *in vivo*, and to eliminate from mouse cells human chromosomes that otherwise are stably transmitted through generations, such as chromosomes 14 and 21. The technique was applied to cultured human cells, such as human induced pluripotent stem cells with trisomy 21, as well as to cancer cells. The work suggested a potential use of CRISPR-Cas9 as a therapeutic strategy for human aneuploidy diseases caused by supernumerary chromosomes [20].

Unexpected chromosomal truncations resulting from a single Cas9 nuclease-induced DSB were generated in human cell lines and primary cells [21]. Also, the CRISPR-Cas9 targeting of genes in close proximity to telomeres can result in chromosome arm truncations in human cell cultures [22].

Besides subtle mutations that can be a byproduct of off-target Cas9 action, the induction of chromosome alterations in human somatic cells highlighted risks of affecting whole genome integrity. The results indicate that large and unexpected karyotype modifications can occur, causing potential severe health problems, that might arise from CRISPR use in human embryo treatment [15].

4. Understanding Somatic Genome Editing

The plethora of studies published on SGE research shows that institutions worldwide are conducting extensive research into SGE. For example, the Somatic Cell Genome Editing (SCGE) Consortium is a National Institutes of Health (NIH) Common Fund organisation that aims to accelerate the development of safe and effective methods to perform gene editing to treat genetic diseases in somatic cells [23]. The SCGE comprises five different initiatives with specific purposes: Biological Effects, Delivery Systems, Genome Editors, Animal Report and Testing Centers, and the Dissemination and Coordinating Center [24].

The SCGE research findings are regularly published. Its notable successes include a reported SGE tool that exhibited potential to treat a mouse model of progeria [25]. Recently, a tiny "nanocapsule" was developed to deliver gene-editing tools to targeted cells more accurately and effectively than previously achieved [26]. Future aims of the SCGE are the creation of therapies to treat rare diseases caused by DNA mutations, e.g., Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy, Huntington Disease, and Cystic Fibrosis. The Consortium recently detailed plans to develop a SCGE

toolkit comprising new genome editors, animal models and human biological systems to be disseminated to the biomedical research community [23].

Public engagement can improve knowledge and change risk and benefit perceptions, but the relationship between these factors remains complex. Currently, invasive procedures are the most common mode of delivery for somatic genome therapies, yet technological advances are likely to bring about less invasive methods of delivery and increase in acceptability. Genome therapies should not be placed under broad blanket regulations; each application should be assessed on its merits [27].

Ethical Appraisal of Somatic Genome Editing

“The recent application of tools, such as CRISPR-Cas9 to edit the human genome with the intention of treating or preventing disease and the gaps in our scientific understanding, in addition to some of the proposed applications of human genome editing, raise ethical issues that have highlighted the need for robust oversight in this area [28]”.

Genome editing tools have a potential use that extends beyond treating somatic disease, with consequences yet unknown. Thus, it is necessary to consider how gene editing might be applied therapeutically while keeping in mind that this technology could be used for purposes other than treating diseases, such as for human enhancement or even to create ‘designer babies’ [29].

1. Somatic Genome Editing: Therapeutic vs. Enhancement

The distinction between editing for therapeutic or enhancement purposes remains important in the discussions of the Ethics of SGE. Grey areas exist in the definitions of ‘therapy’, ‘prevention’ and ‘enhancement’, but the difficulty in making categorical distinctions should not be the occasion to ignore the differences between these actions. For example, nootropics are a diverse group of natural, semi-synthetic and synthetic molecules whose action improves human thinking, learning, and memory, often found in the form of dietary supplements, nutraceuticals and energy drinks. Some nootropic compounds are found in prescription and non-prescription pharmaceutical drugs used especially in cases where these functions are impaired. This would support the argument that gene editing to enhance those cognitive functions is no different from current applications [15]. However, the appraisal of actions is not reducible to their outcomes. Central to the evaluation of an action are its nature, intent, and circumstances in addition to its outcome; to take pills is vastly different from genome editing, as could be the intent and circumstances of both actions too. Significant differences exist between genome-editing interventions and less invasive practices such as taking drugs; a distinction that exists also between taking

medication to remedy deficits and taking them artificially to boost normal capacities [30].

Proponents of enhancement SGE procedures suggest that genomic augmentation of traits can be therapeutic, particularly in correcting defective traits with a genetic origin, or that therapeutic SGE can have an unintended enhancement effect [31]. A simple response is that therapies are intended to produce benefits by curing diseases; albeit in a broad sense they can be considered an enhancement, or may include it as a secondary effect. In the context of this discussion therapeutic SGE refers to correcting defects in the genome that are causes/contributors to diseases and not to modification of traits that are within normal ranges. Genome editing for therapeutic purposes has obtained social acceptance, whereas editing for the purpose of human enhancement is regarded unacceptable by many, and considered by some as contemporary eugenics.

“In medicine, the goal of gene therapy and genetic engineering is to alleviate human suffering and disease. As with all therapies, this goal should be pursued only within the ethical traditions of the profession, which gives primacy to the welfare of the patient. In general, genetic manipulation should be reserved for therapeutic purposes. Efforts to enhance ‘desirable’ characteristics or to ‘improve’ complex human traits are contrary to the ethical tradition of medicine. Because of the potential for abuse, genetic manipulation of non-disease traits unrelated to disease or the eugenic development of offspring may never be justifiable [29].”

2. Values and Principles for Somatic Genome Editing

The Human Genome Editing Committee, sponsored by the National Academy of Medicine and the National Academy of Sciences of the United States, recommended a series of foundational principles to promote well-being, transparency, due care, responsible science, respect for persons, fairness, and translational cooperation.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) issued similar guidelines for the governance of human genome editing: “The technology of human genome editing can be used to expand human knowledge, improve human health and contribute to both collective well-being and the common good. To maximize the positive impact and minimize the potential harms of this technology, procedural and substantive values and principles should guide policies and practices [32].”

The WHO values and principles to inform decisions made about genome editing are: (i) inclusiveness, (ii) caution, (iii) fairness, (iv) social justice, (v) non-discrimination, (vi) equal moral worth, (vii) respect for persons, (viii) solidarity, and (ix) global health justice [32]. Values (iv), (v), (vi) and (vii) are of particular interest to the analysis of SGE.

Value (iv): “In consultation with relevant communities, efforts should be made to ensure access to adequate resources, skills training and capacity-building for researchers, clinicians, policymakers, genetic counsellors and others as needed [32].”

“Use of the CRISPR-Cas9 system to correct pathogenic variants raises concerns about equitable access to therapies by disadvantages groups in society, who are frequently underrepresented in genomic databases. When somatic genome therapies become clinically available these groups would experience limited access to them owing to insufficient genomic data. Also, once commercially available, SGE treatments are likely to be prohibitively expensive for many. To address these justice concerns, the scientific community must ensure diversity in genomic sequences, build trust and partnerships, and advocate for equitable access to emerging therapies. The Human Genome Project is an example of gathering human genomes from around the globe to better understand genomic diversity [33].

Value (v): “To celebrate and promote diversity by rejecting concepts of eugenics and patterns of discrimination based on personal or group characteristics [32].”

Somatic genome editing for enhancement has been likened to eugenics, by disparities between individuals it could result in societal division, as the advantageous capabilities of enhanced individuals will allow them to thrive more [15].

The *Oxford English Dictionary* defines ‘eugenics’ as the science of improving a population (in particular, humans) by controlled breeding for desirable inheritable characteristics. Genetic enhancement advocates argue that science, individual consent, and a determination to improve oneself, and devoid of any element of coercion, form a moral base that makes eugenics permissible. In fact, they suggest there is a moral obligation to produce the best possible genetic children [34]. A core problem with eugenics has been not only its compulsory application in many scientific historical instances, but the classify human traits as ‘good’ or ‘bad’ and to promote social interventions that would make ‘good’ traits become predominant in the human population. There is a fundamental biological reductionism in a conceptual approach that assesses the quality of human beings by ‘good traits’ to be fostered and ‘bad traits’ to be excised from the human population [35].

Proponents of a ‘new eugenics’, argue that enhancement will serve to build a new civilisation where replacement of the genetic lottery of sexual reproduction would lead to an era in which individuals liberated from many diseases and endowed with enhanced traits will be happier, more intelligent and live longer. It is suggested that individual prospective parents take responsibility for the genome editing of

their children [36]. However, this scenario is unlikely to produce a society of better persons; individual choice will influence what particular parents want for their children, and if these choices are not methodical, it will not be possible to build a new civilisation. To achieve a desired improvement in a population requires methodical selection through social regulation, that is, the ‘old eugenics’ [30].

Value (vi): “To recognize and treat all people as having equal moral worth and their interests as deserving of equal moral consideration, with a particular need to recognise and protect the interests of persons with disabilities and of future generations [32].”

The Equal Value Principle (EVP) states that we ought to value disability and non-disability equally [37]; an application of this principle is that disabled and non-disabled persons must be valued equally. To defend eugenics, it is argued that “to avoid bringing a child with a disability into the world says about at all about how we should treat existing people who already have disabilities; just as the fact that we may attempt to cure some of them has no implications for how we should treat those who can’t be cured” [38]. Nonetheless, human embryos containing genetic defects are frequently discarded because they are considered less valuable than those without defects, in violation of the EVP [35].

Another problem is formulated by the Expressivist Argument: “choosing not to conceive or bear a child with a disability expresses and sends out a very negative message about people with disabilities, one that says that it would be better if they had not been born” [38]. In response, new eugenics advocates indicate that other things being equal, it is better to create children with fewer, rather than more, functional limitations, and since this idea is universally applicable it fails to send a message exclusively to people with disabilities. However, if prospective parents avoid having a child solely to exclude the existence of a disabled human being, this is indicative of a prejudicial attitude toward the disabled because it suggests that, at least in some circumstances, the world would be a better place without people with disabilities in it. It is incorrect to conclude that this choice cannot be morally wrong because anyone has the moral right not to have children. The ethical appraisal does not revolve around the morality of deciding to have or not to have children, but on the intention for that decision [35].

The justification for selecting out disability to avoid the harm inflicted on a child that will be born with it is unsound. Employing a current definition of harm as making someone worse than he was before, or making someone worse off than he otherwise would have been, the reasoning does not stand if the only chance of existence is to be born with disability. The greatest

harm to potential human beings is to deny an existence which would ground their personal experiences.

A more impersonal utilitarian justification for avoiding disability is based on overall levels of wellbeing. Considering the overall wellbeing in society, it seems that choosing an embryo with potential disability entails choosing a lower overall level of wellbeing in the world than choosing one without disabilities. This argument highlights that human value is assessed by ability and capacity, and individuals with disabilities or lower capabilities are deemed to have lower value than others [15]. The reasoning implies also that on average, disabled persons have worse lives than non-disabled persons, which is attributed to a reduced capacity to flourish. This conclusion can be answered in two ways: (i) disabled persons can overcome disadvantages and have highly worthwhile life. In fact, there are many such cases, and famous examples include the profoundly deaf Beethoven, who gave humanity such incomparable music; the blind poet Homer; the paralysed scientist Stephen Hawking; and countless other less well known but no less genuine cases of individuals with both disability and high levels of achievement [38]. (ii) There is an association between 'flourishing' and 'quality of life', but neither is easily or simply measurable, and both contain a strong subjective element. Thus, to measure wellbeing using either or both concepts is highly problematic. "So people who are disabled don't always have lower levels of wellbeing than those who are not disabled, and in those cases where individuals do have a poorer quality of life on account of their disability, much of this differential can be reduced by appropriate physical and social arrangements [38]."

Value (vii): "To respect the wishes of competent individuals regarding the most intimate aspects of their lives, including their health and their reproductive options. In addition, a commitment to promote the best interests of individuals who are not competent to make decisions for themselves" [32].

This principle impacts on a wide range of issues, namely, calculations of risk assessment and safety, patent monitoring (potentially for long periods), reimbursement, equity in access to new therapies, particular protection for vulnerable populations (e.g., fetuses, children), and informed consent [39].

The effectiveness of SGE may have improved therapeutic chances when it is performed early in life. "Multisystemic or extremely early onset diseases may require editing of somatic cells of a fetus prior to delivery because postnatal interventions would come too late to benefit the child or are technically very challenging. In addition, the great developmental plasticity of the fetus might make more effective fetal editing than postnatal editing; for example, it would be simpler to revert a disease-causing variant that affects

every neuron in the brain in an early fetus than in a newborn infant" [35]. Therapeutic genome editing could be performed *ex vivo* in cells harvested from the fetus, edited outside the body, and then transplanted back in the fetus, or *in vivo*, in which case the editing machinery would be delivered to the fetus to modify cells *in situ* [40].

Performing SGE during fetal development needs to address the difficulties that the ethical demarcations that distinguish somatic and germline genome editing are less clear, that there is an increased change genome alterations will be inherited by future generations, and that it involves risks to two individuals: mother and child. Generally, somatic genome therapy has been applied to consenting persons, targeted to specific cells of the recipient, and applied to an individual and not to future generations. However, in fetal somatic genome therapy, two individuals potentially are impacted by the treatment (mother and child), and since treatment takes place at an early stage of human development, it may have effects on future generations [41]. Moreover, complications such as infection, preterm labour, and fetal loss and theoretically possible with *in utero* genome therapy and maternal safety is of paramount importance [42]. For these reasons, acceptable risks of therapeutic genome editing can be significantly higher than for enhancement in keeping proportion between risks and benefits. Thus, considering patient safety, the risks for mother and child in fetal somatic genome enhancement will be unacceptable.

Discussion

The progress of methods to edit the genome has been growing apace in the last few years and somatic genome editing holds great future promise. Nonetheless, many problems regarding safety, efficiency and reliability are unresolved. Owing to the complexity of interactions between components of the human genome and the newness of current techniques, the current impossibility to foresee all possible side effects resulting from the manipulation of the targeted DNA remains a major problem [15].

Therapies that employ SGE could be permitted under strict guidelines because they generally involve patient consent, affect one person, and are often targeted toward a specific area of the human body [42].

There are grey areas of overlap between SGE for therapy and for enhancement, but they can be resolved. A criterion that would serve to differentiate between therapy and enhancement is that SGE should be employed to improve traits to the levels possessed by normal individuals through genetic inheritance or personal effort, and not to obtain social advantages. The basis of this proposal is that becoming normal eliminates disease which by definition, is abnormal, and yet confers no 'social advantage' to a patient [27]. Concurrently, it is important that inclusive SGE

innovations need to be developed to include the diversity of the human population and human experiences [2].

Ethical discussions require a set of core values accepted as reference to analyse a problem [27]. If a fundamental value is that the patient is an individual human being, then she/she cannot be an instrument to serve other aims. Thus individuals, and in particular children, must not be regarded as products to be improved to achieve whatever ideal and in the process diminishing their uniqueness.

An ethical problem posed by SGE is the cost associated with its use that could create a public divide between privileged and underprivileged persons in society. In particular, SGE for enhancement commonly is supported by various types of ‘genetic determinism’ arguments that overestimate the value genetic factors. Investing large amounts of resources to make enhancement publicly available, privileges genetic causes over other factors which carry greater social importance.

Conclusion

There are successful applications of SGE to monogenic inherited disorders and more are expected, but a current limit to a general implementation of this type of editing is the impossibility at present to predict all possible effects of changing regions of the genome. Future better understanding of the interactions between different parts of the genome and improvement of the specificity and reliability of the tools employed for editing will enable expansion of the utilisation of SGE.

Progress in the knowledge of human genetics and genome architecture has yielded a greater realisation that many traits depend on a large number of genes that contribute a small amount to their phenotype, and whose interactions are not well understood, e.g. height, intelligence, etc. This intrinsic polygenic characteristic of gene-trait relations poses a ceiling to altering personal phenotypes by genetic manipulation. The possibility of correcting errors with genetic origin and improving the health of human beings has the positive ethical value of beneficence. In appraising the ethical issues of non-therapeutic enhancement of traits with the desire to improve persons, it is necessary to consider that the foundations of human relations are the equality and ethical behaviour of individuals. The basic status of a person as a member of society is not defined by its abilities; disabled people are fundamentally equal to anyone else simply because they are human. It is difficult to discern how a view promoting the value of human enhancement as a prerequisite for the progress of humanity will accord the same ethical treatment to all human beings. This perspective is based on a reductionist anthropology that ‘objectifies’ persons; individuals become ‘things to

be improved’. Application of technical methods to human enhancement challenge the self-determination of individuals, question their integrity and agency, and disregard their subjectivity.

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